

Short Communication

Real-life use of bronchodilators and inhaled corticosteroids in cystic fibrosis and non-CF bronchiectasis, Do guidelines matter?

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1. Introduction

Bronchiectasis is a pulmonary condition defined by an abnormal dilation of the bronchial lumen. Patients will typically have a frequent cough, often productive of sputum with purulent components, and there may be episodes of acute worsening of symptoms called pulmonary exacerbations [1]. It is a heterogeneous condition known to be associated with or caused by numerous etiologies, both pulmonary and extrapulmonary, including cystic fibrosis (CF) [2]. Bronchiectasis is often accompanied by impaired mucociliary clearance creating an environment susceptible to persistent infection and inflammation, inferred by the imaging appearance of thickening of the bronchial wall and/or mucus plugs [3].

There are several pulmonary therapies that have been approved for the treatment of CF lung disease but none for other causes of bronchiectasis [4]. Nonetheless, there are clinical guidelines that recommend against routine use of specific therapies, in particular inhaled bronchodilators and inhaled corticosteroids (ICS), yet these remain the most commonly prescribed treatments for both groups [5–8].

2. What do the guidelines actually recommend?

2.1. Inhaled bronchodilators

The CF pulmonary guidelines were based on a systematic review of the literature. Although there were multiple studies of short-(SABA) and long-acting (LABA) β 2-adrenergic receptor agonists conducted in

persons with CF, they were generally small and deemed to provide insufficient evidence to recommend their chronic daily use [8,9].

In the case of bronchiectasis, there are multiple sets of guidelines including those by the European Respiratory Society (ERS), the British Thoracic Society (BTS), and the Spanish Society of Pulmonology (SEPAR) [5–7], whom also found limited evidence upon which to base recommendations. The ERS did not recommend routine use of LABA unless there was significant breathlessness or concomitant asthma or COPD with objective airway obstruction. They also suggested SABA could be used before physiotherapy or inhaled medications to improve their tolerability, but these were admittedly weak recommendations [5]. The BTS recommended that bronchodilators could be used in patients with symptoms, such as dyspnea [6]. SEPAR also recommended SABA before respiratory physiotherapy and the use of inhaled medications but offered more caution for LABA, reserving their use for those patients with symptomatic airflow obstruction, provided the advantages outweigh the adverse effects [7].

2.2. Inhaled corticosteroids

A systematic review of the CF literature likewise found no clinical benefit to ICS, albeit in small trials, and so the CF pulmonary guidelines recommended against their chronic use [8,9]. The ERS, BTS, and SEPAR guidelines also found little evidence and recommended against the use of ICS in bronchiectasis [5,6]; however, they both offered the caveat that the recommendation excludes those patients who have concomitant eosinophilic COPD and/or asthma [5,6]. SEPAR recommended caution

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against their use because of potential increased risk of infection, suggesting they be limited to those patients with bronchial hyperreactivity, asthma, or significant bronchorrhea that cannot be controlled with other treatments [7].

3. Current scenario in the use of bronchodilators in bronchiectasis and CF

Despite these general recommendations, inhaled bronchodilators and ICS are used in most patients with bronchiectasis, including those with CF (Table 1) [10–13]. These data are derived from multiple patient registries that track patient prescriptions (which may not mean usage). Bronchodilators are prescribed for the majority of patients, typically >70 % of them, with somewhat lower use in India and South Korea [10]. The lone exception is China [14] where only 10 % of patients are reported to be prescribed bronchodilators. In CF the use of bronchodilators is even higher (95 % of patients) [11]. Similarly for ICS, there is a very high reported prescription rate in most registries, often >50 % for those with bronchiectasis, but again lower in South Korea [10] and China [11] with 16.1 and 3.6 % respectively. There is reduced usage reported in CF patients but it is still approximately one-fourth of the population [8]. Even accounting for the caveats provided in the guidelines for the use of inhaled bronchodilators and ICS (i.e. when there is concomitant COPD, asthma or allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (ABPA)), these rates of prescriptions are excessive. The reported rates of asthma and COPD in these registries (Table 1) are much lower than the prescription rates. However, we must acknowledge the limitations of registries. For example, they may not capture patient-reported symptoms (e.g.

dyspnea) without a formal diagnosis of asthma or COPD.

4. Why is there such high use of bronchodilators and inhaled corticosteroids in bronchiectasis and CF?

4.1. Inhaled bronchodilators

SABA, LABA, and long-acting muscarinic agonist (LAMA) bronchodilators are the most widely used medications in COPD and asthma, given their well-established efficacy and safety demonstrated through randomized controlled trials [15,16]. COPD is a known associated comorbidity (and possible etiology) of bronchiectasis. Indeed, many patients have been incorrectly (or incompletely) diagnosed with COPD before the eventual diagnosis of bronchiectasis. Functionally, up to 40 % of patients with bronchiectasis exhibit chronic airflow obstruction [17], which may be partially reversible with SABA. Patients with CF are not thought to have classical features of COPD, but they certainly develop progressive obstructive airways physiology. In addition, some patients with bronchiectasis or CF will have features of asthma [18]. But again, the numbers of patients reported to have either COPD or asthma lie well below the numbers with prescriptions for bronchodilators.

These medications may have value in preventing bronchospasm associated with inhaled therapies and clinical trials often require the use of SABA prior to the use of the inhaled treatment under investigation [19,20]. These recommendations are made despite limited scientific evidence. Finally, and most likely, clinicians have a high level of comfort using bronchodilators, believing them to be generally safe, rarely causing adverse effects unless administered at very high doses.

Table 1

Data from available registries of bronchiectasis and cystic fibrosis regarding prescription of bronchodilators and inhaled corticosteroids.

Data set Region	Bronchiectasis								Cystic Fibrosis	
	^a EMBARC Europe	^b Historical Spain	^c RIBRON Spain	^d BRR USA	^e IBR India	^f ABR Australia	^g KMBARC South Korea	^h China BE Registry	ⁱ CFPR USA	^j ECFS Patient Registry Europe
Number of patients included	16,963	2047	2615	1826	2195	566	931	16,338	33,288	56,144
Period	2015–2022	2002–2011	2015- present	2008–2014	2015–2017	2016–2018	2018–2021	2020–2025	2023	2023
Bronchodilator use, %	78.6 %	76.5 %	78 %	70 %*	56.6 %	NR	50.5 %	10.9 %	95 %	50.6 % (peds) 71.2 % (adults)
Inhaled steroid use, %	51.3 %	68.1 %	66.2 %	45 %*	63.2 %	NR	16.1 %	3.6 %	24.8 %	17.5 % (peds) 35.4 % (adults)
Reported asthma, %	6.9 %	5.4 %	7.8 %	29 %	2.5 %	3.7 %	5 %	1.5 %	30.2 %	NR
Reported COPD, %	8.1 %	7.7 %	10.9 %	20 %	5.3 %	3.4 %	6.4 %	4.9 %	NR	NR
Reported ABPA, %	2.8 %	0.9 %	0.9 %	NR	8.9 %	4.1 %	0.5 %	1.3 %	4.2 %	4 %

Table legend: EMBARC: European Multi-centre Bronchiectasis Audit and Research Collaboration; RIBRON: SEPAR Spanish Bronchiectasis Registry; BRR: Bronchiectasis Research Registry; IBR: Indian Bronchiectasis Registry; ABR: Australian Bronchiectasis Registry; KMBARC: Korean Multi-centre Bronchiectasis Audit and Research Collaboration; CFPR: Cystic Fibrosis Foundation Patient Registry; ECFS: European Cystic Fibrosis Society; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ABPA: allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis; NR: not reported.

The data were abstracted from the following resources:

^a Chalmers JD, Polverino E, Crichton ML, et al. Bronchiectasis in Europe: data on disease characteristics from the European Bronchiectasis registry (EMBARC). *Lancet Respir Med* 2023; 11: 637–649.

^b Oliveira C, Padilla A, Martínez-García MÁ, et al. Etiology of Bronchiectasis in a Cohort of 2047 Patients. An Analysis of the Spanish Historical Bronchiectasis Registry. *Arch Bronconeumol*. 2017; 53: 366–374.

^c Martínez-García MA, Villa C, Dobarganes Y, et al. RIBRON: The Spanish Online Bronchiectasis Registry. Characterization of the First 1912 Patients. *Arch Bronconeumol*. 2021; 57: 28–35.

^d Aksamit TR, O'Donnell AE, Barker A, et al. Adult patients with bronchiectasis: a first look at the US Bronchiectasis Research Registry. *Chest*. 2017; 151: 982–992.

^e Dhar R, Singh S, Talwar D, et al. Bronchiectasis in India: results from the European Multicentre Bronchiectasis Audit and Research Collaboration (EMBARC) and Respiratory Research Network of India Registry. *Lancet Glob Health* 2019; 7: e1269 - e1279.

^f Visser SK, Bye PTP, Fox GJ, et al. Australian adults with bronchiectasis: The first report from the Australian Bronchiectasis Registry. *Respir Med*. 2019 Aug;155:97–103.

^g Lee H, Choi H, Sim YS, et al. KMBARC registry: protocol for a multicentre observational cohort study on non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis in Korea. *BMJ Open*. 2020; 10: e034090.

^h Xu JF, Zheng HZ, Lu HW, et al. Baseline characteristics of patients in the Chinese Bronchiectasis Registry (BE-China): a multicentre prospective cohort study. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2025; 13: 166–176.

ⁱ Cystic Fibrosis Foundation Patient Registry. 2023 Annual Data Report. Bethesda, Maryland.

^j ECFSPR Annual Report 2023, Zolin A, Adamoli A, Bakkeheim E, 2025.

Nonetheless, there are potential cardiovascular side effects (e.g. tachycardia, palpitations, arrhythmias) and its potential impact on patients with cardiac comorbidities should not be overlooked. The additional impact on cost and treatment burden should not be ignored.

4.2. Inhaled corticosteroids

The airways disease in bronchiectasis, including CF, is driven by persistent and excessive inflammation [3]. The inflammation seen in bronchiectasis and CF can share certain characteristics with that of COPD and asthma, with some patient showing elevated levels of eosinophils [21–24]. Some patients may also meet criteria for ABPA, which is treated like asthma. However, the inflammation in bronchiectasis and CF has a predominance of neutrophils [3], which are not thought to be responsive to corticosteroids. The development of inhaled drug combinations, containing both bronchodilators and corticosteroids, likely makes it even easier for clinicians to initiate therapy in patients and, again, there is a general comfort in the use of these products with few reported adverse effects.

Nevertheless, caution must be exercised when using ICS, especially at high doses, because they are also potent immunosuppressants. Patients with bronchiectasis and CF commonly have persistent bacterial infection in the airways [24,25]. The immunosuppression associated with ICS has been reported to associate with exacerbations of airways disease. Recent studies support this concern; for example, one study demonstrated that in patients with bronchiectasis, the use of ICS (in comparison with macrolides) significantly increased both the number and severity of exacerbations, even approaching a statistically significant increase in mortality [26].

5. Conclusions

It is not easy to determine the true reasons behind the overutilization of bronchodilators and ICS in patients with bronchiectasis and CF worldwide, despite a clear lack of scientific evidence and official recommendations against their use beyond the coexistence of asthma or COPD. Clinicians should re-evaluate the need for bronchodilators and/or ICS, and rather than merely continuing the medications they should query whether their continuance is justified. Or, when starting one (or both) of these medications, they should clearly define the intent and expected outcomes, and consider stopping them after a trial if those expectations are not achieved.

We acknowledge that the guidelines based their recommendations on limited evidence. Although it is likely that some patients will benefit from the use of these medications, it is equally likely that many patients are prescribed them unnecessarily adding cost, burden, and potential adverse effects. Greater efforts should be made to determine the true necessity of these medications in each patient and consideration for withdrawal from patients currently using them. Although it is unlikely there will be studies evaluating bronchodilators or ICS in bronchiectasis or CF in the near term given competing priorities, there remains a need for pragmatic trials of de-prescribing in these patients. Indeed, a blinded, controlled study of ICS withdrawal in CF and bronchiectasis patients resulted in no adverse outcomes [27,28] demonstrating that such a practice could be done safely.

Guarantor statement

Patrick Flume and M.A. Martinez-Garcia are the guarantor of the content of the manuscript.

Contributors

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All authors has any financial and personal relationships with other people or organizations that could inappropriately influence (bias) this work.

References

- [1] Aliberti S, Goeminne PC, O'Donnell AE, et al. Criteria and definitions for the radiological and clinical diagnosis of bronchiectasis in adults for use in clinical trials: international consensus recommendations. *Lancet Respir Med* 2022;10(3): 298–306.
- [2] Lonni S, Chalmers JD, Goeminne PC, et al. Etiology of non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis in adults and its correlation to disease severity, 12. *Ann Am Thorac Soc*; 2015. p. 1764–70.
- [3] Lynch DA, Newell J, Hale V, et al. Correlation of CT findings with clinical evaluations in 261 patients with symptomatic bronchiectasis. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 1999;173:53–8.
- [4] Li D, Schneider-Futschik EK. Current and emerging inhaled antibiotics for chronic pulmonary *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in cystic fibrosis. *Antibiotics (Basel)* 2023 Feb 28;12(3):484.
- [5] Polverino E, Goeminne PC, McDonnell MJ, et al. European Respiratory Society guidelines for the management of adult bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir J* 2017;50(3): 1700629.
- [6] Hill AT, Sullivan AL, Chalmers JD, et al. British Thoracic Society guideline for bronchiectasis in adults. *Thorax* 2019;74:1–69.
- [7] Martínez-García MÁ, Máiz L, Oliveira C, et al. Spanish guidelines on treatment of bronchiectasis in adults. *Arch Bronconeumol (Engl Ed)* 2018;54(2):88–98.
- [8] Jr Mogayzel PJ, Naureckas ET, Robinson KA, et al. Cystic fibrosis pulmonary guidelines. Chronic medications for maintenance of lung health. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2013 Apr 1;187(7):680–9.
- [9] Flume PA, O'Sullivan BP, Robinson KA, et al. Cystic fibrosis pulmonary guidelines: chronic medications for maintenance of lung health. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2007 Nov 15;176(10):957–69.
- [10] Oscullo G, Bekki A, de la Rosa D, Martínez-García MA. Registries for bronchiectasis in the world: an opportunity for international collaboration. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis* 2025 May 25;29(5):199–201.
- [11] CFF registry: Cystic Fibrosis Foundation Patient Registry, 2023 Annual Data Report. Bethesda, Maryland.
- [12] ECFSPR Annual Report 2023, Zolin A., Adamoli A., Bakkeheim E., 2025.
- [13] Oscullo G, García-Ortega A, Guan WJ, Martínez-García MA. Bronchodilators and inhaled corticosteroids use in major global bronchiectasis registries. *J Thorac Dis* 2025;s396–401.
- [14] Xu JF, Zheng HZ, Lu HW, et al. Baseline characteristics of patients in the Chinese bronchiectasis Registry (BE-China): a multicentre prospective cohort study. *Lancet Respir Med* 2025;13(2):166–76.
- [15] Cazzola M, Page C. Long-acting bronchodilators in COPD: where are we now and where are we going? *Breathe* 2014;10(2):110–20.
- [16] Mkorombindo T, Dransfield MT. Inhaled corticosteroids in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: benefits and risks. *Clin Chest Med* 2020;41(3):475–84.
- [17] Radovanovic D, Santus P, Blasi F, et al. A comprehensive approach to lung function in bronchiectasis. *Respir Med* 2018;145:120–9.
- [18] G Kartal Öztürk, Eşki A, Demir E, et al. Asthma-like symptom or "cystic fibrosis asthma"? *Tuberk Toraks* 2021;69(2):167–76.
- [19] Martínez-García MÁ, Oscullo G, García-Ortega A, et al. Inhaled corticosteroids in adults with non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis: from bench to bedside. A Narrative Review. *Drugs*. 2022;82(14):1453–68.
- [20] Martínez-García MÁ, Oscullo G, García-Ortega A, et al. Rationale and clinical use of bronchodilators in adults with bronchiectasis. *Drugs* 2022;82(1):1–13.
- [21] Tashkin DP, Wechsler ME. Role of eosinophils in airway inflammation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis* Jan 17 2018;13: 335–49.
- [22] Shoemark A, Shteinberg M, De Soyza A, et al. Characterization of eosinophilic bronchiectasis: a European multicohort study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2022;205(8):894–902.
- [23] Martínez-García MÁ, Méndez R, Oliveira C, et al. The U-shaped relationship between eosinophil count and bronchiectasis severity: the effect of inhaled corticosteroids. *Chest* 2023;164(3):606–13.
- [24] Martínez-García MÁ, de la Rosa-Carrillo D, Soler-Cataluña JJ, et al. Bronchial infection and temporal evolution of bronchiectasis in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Clin Infect Dis* 2021;72(3):403–10.
- [25] Lyczak JB, Cannon CL, Pier GB. Lung infections associated with cystic fibrosis. *Clin Microbiol Rev* 2002;15(2):194–222.

- [26] Henkle E, Curtis JR, Chen L, et al. Comparative risks of chronic inhaled corticosteroids and macrolides for bronchiectasis. *Eur Respir J* 2019;54(1): 1801896.
- [27] Balfour-Lynn IM, Lees B, Hall P, et al. Multicenter randomized controlled trial of withdrawal of inhaled corticosteroids in cystic fibrosis. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2006;173(12):1356–62.
- [28] Guran T, Ersu R, Karadag B, et al. Withdrawal of inhaled steroids in children with non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis. *J Clin Pharm Ther* 2008;33(6):603–11.